

Additive manufacturing and microstructure effects on thermal and mechanical properties of ply-hybrid carbon and glass fibre composites

Cristina Pascual-González^{1,2*}, Jesús García-Moreno Caraballo^{1,3}, Iker Lizarralde^{1,4,5}, David Garoz Gómez^{1,6} and Juan P. Fernández-Blázquez¹

¹IMDEA Materials Institute, C/Eric Kandel 2, Getafe, 28906, Madrid, Spain.

²Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid, CSIC, Cantoblanco, 28049 Madrid, Spain, C/Tulipán s/n, Móstoles, 28049, Madrid, Spain.

³Escuela Politécnica Superior y de Arquitectura, Universidad Nebrija, C/ de Sta. Cruz de Marcenado 27, Madrid, 28015, Madrid, Spain.

⁴Department of Materials Science, Polytechnic University of Madrid, E. T. S. de Ingenieros de Caminos., C/ del Prof. Aranguren, 3, Madrid, 28040, Madrid, Spain.

⁵Hexcel Composites S.L., C/ Bruselas 10-16, Parla, 28983, Madrid, Spain.

⁶Instituto de Fusión Nuclear “Guillermo Velarde”, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, C/José Gutiérrez Abascal 2, Madrid, 28040, Madrid, Spain.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): cristina.pascual@csic.es;
Contributing authors: jgarciamoreno@nebrija.es;
iker.lizarralde@imdea.org; david.garoz@upm.es;
juanpedro.fernandez@imdea.org;

Abstract

The fiber hybridization in high-strength composites is one of the most researched strategies to enhance their limited toughness. In this work, hybrid composites at laminate level by stacking together plies of carbon and glass fiber were prepared using fused filament fabrication (FFF) technique. The large void content and the poor adhesion between layers attributed to this technology are overcome by the addition of an optimized thermo-pressurised treatment. The analysis of post-processing temperature effects on the microstructural, thermal and interlaminar properties of additive manufactured hybrid composites, revealed a progressive porosity reduction preserving the dimensional accuracy. The enhancement of mechanical properties is due to different contributions that occurred during post-processing: (i) drying effect, which reduces the plasticization of the composites; (ii) improvement of interface adhesion due to the miscibility of polymers; and (iii) significant porosity reduction (below 1%). This work opens a wider space of possibilities, since FFF allows more complex designs than traditional composite manufacturing, and additionally provides an approach to promote molecular diffusion at the interface, which is the most critical region of FFF parts.

Keywords: Ply-hybrid composites; Carbon fibre; Glass fibre; fused filament fabrication; Post-processing; Thermoplastic composite.

1 Introduction

The use of carbon fiber reinforced composites (CFRC) is widely spread in sectors such as transport, sports and construction. The main reason is their low density and high stiffness and strength, in spite of their relatively low toughness. Many research efforts have been directed toward the enhancement of the energy absorption and damage tolerance of CFRP laminates under impact loading. Various strategies have been reported for improving the impact behavior of CFRC, such as the dispersion of nanoparticles in the matrix composite [1], the incorporation of cellular shell structures or foams in sandwich structures [2] and the hybridization with high toughness fibers, such as glass fibers [3, 4]. The high ductility of glass fiber (GF) may control the brittle fracture of carbon fiber (CF), which, in turn, enhances the mechanical properties of the specimen. Recently, 3D printing of CFRC has undergone considerable developments, due to its potential to fabricate complex and highly customized composites with a mechanical behaviour adapted to a concrete application [5–10]. Indeed, this technology provides greater flexibility in design and fiber placement, which is very difficult by traditional methods. Moreover, automated additive manufacturing routes reduce labour operator, costs and waste. Specifically, FFF (fused filament fabrication) method consists of depositing layer-by-layer continuous fibers that are pre-impregnated thermoplastic following 3D model. One of the potential benefits of this technology

is the fabrication of dispersed CFRP (composites with non-conventional fiber orientations). Recently, Garoz Gómez et al. have proposed a methodology to design 3D printed CFRP composite with optimized mechanical behavior under critical load conditions[11]. 3D printing of hybrid continuous fiber composites is not widespread, because current commercial 3D printers do not present an automated mechanism that dynamically changes the materials. However, some works reported hybrid composites using a commercial 3D printer, such as Swolfs et al that demonstrated enhanced translamina fracture toughness through intra-lamina hybridization of continuous carbon and glass fibres[12]. Zia et al have recently reported a significant improvement in damage tolerance impact of 3D printed composites, through intra-yarn hybridization of continuous carbon and aramid fibers [13]. Wang et al. obtained a significant improvement in the energy absorption in 3D printed composites by the interply hybridization of continuous carbon and aramid fibers [14]. The increase of the aramid fiber content led to enhanced impact strength, but a decrease in tensile and flexural strength [15]. However, all these works highlighted that the defects caused by FFF technology have a great influence on the mechanical behaviors of printed composites [14]. Pascual-González et al. proposed a thermo-consolidation step to overcome the poor interlaminar bonding and to reduce the high void content of the 3D printed CFRC [16]. Markforged 3D printer (model: MarkTwo) is the only commercial technology for continuous fiber composite based on FFF method. Nevertheless, this equipment is limited in terms of manufacturing options and the matrix/fiber combinations are predetermined. A previous investigation showed the continuous carbon fibers were embedded into amorphous polyamide, while the continuous glass fibers into semi-crystalline polyamide [8]. Therefore, fiber hybridization also requires polymer matrix hybridization. The interlaminar adhesion in a layered structure can be improved if the two different polymers are miscible. Following this idea, Alvaredo-Atienza et al. demonstrated the formation of a well-adhered interfacial region in multilayered PEEK/PEI films, being PEEK a semi-crystalline polymer and PEI an amorphous polymer[17]. Subsequently, Toro et al. optimized the processing conditions for this system [18]. The optimum consolidation temperature was close to the melting point of PEEK, in order to reach a viscous state and, consequently, the molecular mobility is enough to achieve interpenetration. The diffusion of the polymer chains creates a physical union, which is an interesting strategy to overcome the weak bonding between layers in FFF parts. Indeed, Srinivas et al demonstrated the interlayer stereocomplex formation by depositing alternating layers of poly(D-lactide) and poly(L-lactides), significantly enhanced the mechanical properties of 3D printed parts [19]. Moreover, improvement in the interlayer strength as result of promoting the miscibility of two different polymers in 3D printed parts by FFF has been demonstrated in PLA-PMMA [20], PP-PH [21] and PAEK-PEEK systems[22]. This work analyses the post-processing temperatures' effect on the properties of 3D printed GF-CF hybrid composites. The

final objective is to have an optimized fabrication route for high-quality hybrid composites using a commercial 3D printer.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 3D printer, hybrid specimens and post-processing

The hybrid composites were manufactured using a commercial 3D printer MarkTwo, based on FFF technology. The commercial filaments consist of a bunch of continuous fibers (CF and GF, separately) impregnated with thermoplastic polymer. As previously mentioned, continuous CF are embedded into an amorphous Polyamide (PA) and the continuous GF into a semi-crystalline polyamide (PA6). In order to evaluate the hybrid effect, the thermal and mechanical properties are compared to each component separately. The characterization of GF composite is presented in this work, while the CF composite properties are taken from a previous work [16]. Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of the 3D printed samples, which consist of rectangular unidirectional composites of (a) GF and (b) hybrid-ply CF and GF composites. The GF composite is made of glass fiber reinforced semicrystalline polyamide, PA6; the hybrid composite consists of carbon and glass fibers reinforced amorphous and semicrystalline polyamides, PA and PA6 respectively. GF and hybrid laminates have a total of 23 layers with dimensions of 105 mm x 28 mm x 2.5, in order to facilitate the comparison with CF laminates[16]. In the case of hybrid composite, the symmetric laminate for short-beam tests is obtained by the following stacking sequence: 5 layers of CF, 5 layers of GF, 3 layers of CF, 5 layers of GF, and 5 layers of CF.

Eiger is the 3D printing software developed by Markforged, to import .stl files (*STereoLithography*) and to customize printing settings. This platform automatically calculates the trajectories of the fiber, maximizing the quantity of reinforcement and ensuring the continuity of the fibers. However, the software does not allow printing two different reinforcement materials on the same part. Therefore, the strategy for printing hybrid laminates was to launch a print job by fixing GF as unique reinforcement and programming pauses after the deposition of each layer. The CF filament was manually changed, and this process was repeated five times. The CF was acceptably deposited with the GF printing parameters. The 3D printing parameters, such as extrusion temperature, printing speed and layer thickness, are fixed in Eiger for each commercial material. Only a few parameters regarding the fibre placement can be personalized: (i) the infill percentage was 100%, (ii) the fiber fill type was isotropic, (iii) the fiber angle was 0°, (iv) the brim was not activated and (v) one contour, one layer in the top and other at the bottom of the semicrystalline PA6 were added in all 3D printed specimen by default. Subsequently, the specimens were post-processed in the hot plates (Fortine PressesR[®]) at 150°C, 165°C and 175°C during 15 minutes (heating speed of 10°C/min) applying 1 MPa [16]. The internal defects of 3D printed and post-processed samples were observed

Fig. 1 Schematic representation of the 3D printed samples. (a) Continuous GF composite of 23 layers. The white path represents the trajectory of continuous GF deposited by FFF and the orange matrix corresponds to the semi-crystalline polyamide (PA6); (b) Continuous hybrid CF and GF composite of 23 layers (5 layers of CF, 5 layers of GF, 3 layers of CF, 5 layers of GF and 5 layers of CF). The black and white path represents the trajectory of continuous CF and GF, respectively. The blue and orange matrices correspond to the semicrystalline (PA6) and amorphous (PA) polyamide, respectively.

by the automated C-Scan ultrasonic scanning (TRITON 1500, Tecnitest). X-ray computed micro-tomography was used to examine the microstructure and quantify the porosity content (General Electric Phoenix Nanotom 160 kV). The target was molybdenum, 0-mode nanofocus and no additional filter materials were used. The voltage of the X-ray tube for the scan was 50 kV and the current was 200 μ A.

2.2 Thermomechanical characterisation of 3D printed hybrid composites

The weight evolution as a function of temperature up to 1000°C was obtained by TGA equipment (Q50, TA Instruments). Differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, model Q200, TA Instruments) was used to study the thermal behavior of hybrid composites and the miscibility of PA/PA6 polymers. Samples of approximately 5 mg were heated up from room temperature up to 250°C (heating rate of 10 °C/min), then cooled to -10°C and finally heated again under the same conditions. The thermo-mechanical stability from -100°C to 230°(heating rate of 3°C/min) was studied in single cantilever bending mode by dynamic mechanical analysis (Q800, TA Instruments), on unidirectional rectangles coupons of 30 mm x 10 mm, cut from 3D printed hybrid laminates of 25 mm of thickness. The experiments were performed at a frequency of 1 Hz and 30 μ m of amplitude. The interlaminar response of 3D printed hybrid composite was characterized according to the standard ASTM D 2344 [23]. The sample dimensions for short-beam test depended on the resulting thickness after the compaction stage. The length and width were six and two times

its thickness, respectively. The tests were carried out in an electromechanical machine (Instron 3384) with a 5 kN load cell at a loading speed of 1 mm/min. The three point fixture was set with the appropriate span for each sample as 4 times its thickness. The elastic behavior was compared with the simulation of the virtual experiment based on finite elements.

3 Results

The weight loss evolution with temperature for GF and CF-GF composites untreated and post-processed at different temperatures are shown in Figures 2 (a) and (b), respectively. The inset graphs of Figures 2 (a) and (b) show a zoom of TGA curves between room temperature and 150°C in order to evaluate the water content. Untreated GF and CF-GF composites show a 2% of weight loss. After post-processing, the release of water in GF composites is slightly higher than in CF-GF composites, which means the semi-crystalline matrix (PA6) absorbs more water from the environment than the amorphous matrix (PA). In a previous work [8], we concluded that the amorphous polyamide may correspond to PA6/3T polyamide by examining the thermo-mechanical properties, while semicrystalline is PA6. The structure of PA6 presents more polar groups (amides and carbonyl groups) than PA 6/3T in its repetitive units. Thus, PA6 may present more hydrophilic behaviour than PA 6/3T. However, both composites present a systematic reduction of weight loss with increasing post-processing temperature, which corroborates the drying effect reported for 3D printed CFRC (Figures 2 (a) and (b))[16]. No further effects dependent on post-processing temperatures are found. All the GF composites undergo one simple thermal decomposition step, that starts at 370°C and reached the maximum weight loss at 430°C (Figure 2 (a)). The residues correspond to the mass fraction of fibers in GF composites, which is approximately 50%. All the TGA curves for CF-GF hybrid composites show two degradation steps (Figure 2 (b)). The first one corresponds to the thermal degradation of both matrices, which is independent of the post-processing temperature. The CF's degradation starts at 600°C and completely finishes at 800 °C [8]. The CF mass fraction is approximately 30%. The final residue corresponds to the mass fraction of GF in CF-GF composites, which is approximately 20%.

DSC curves of GF and hybrid CF-GF composites untreated and post-processed at 150°C, 165°C and 175°C are shown in Figures 3 (a) and (b), respectively. In each graph are shown first heating, cooling and second heating. The arrows indicate the direction of the temperature increase. First heating curves of GF composites (Figure 3 (a)) exhibit broad endothermic peaks between 75°C- 100°C for all samples. This feature is ascribed to water evaporation and does not permit observing the glass transition of the semi-crystalline matrix (PA6). Increasing the temperature, the untreated sample presents a single asymmetric melting peak at 203°C. A shoulder at lower temperatures emerges for the composites treated at 150°C, while a narrow melting point at higher temperatures is observed for GF composites post-processed at 165°C.

Fig. 2 TGA graphs of (a) GF and (b) CF-GF composites, untreated and post-processed at 150 °C, 165 °C and 170 °C. The inset graphs show a zoom of the TGA curves between 25 °C and 150 °C.

Finally, an extra peak at higher temperatures is observed in the samples treated at 175 °C. All of these variations in the melting profile after the post-processing are due to the annealing process at different temperatures between glass transition and melting temperatures, in which new crystals are formed and their melting temperatures depend on post-processing temperature. Giving melting peaks at higher temperatures when the post-processing was also carried out at higher temperatures. During the cooling, a unique exothermic peak at 160 °C is observed in all the samples and remains unaffected upon post-processing temperatures. Finally, the DSC profiles during the second heating of GF composites show the same appearance for untreated and post-processed samples. The glass transition of GF composites appears around 42 °C ($T_{g(PA6)}$) and the melting point at 198 °C ($T_{m(PA6)}$), that also presents a shoulder at lower temperatures. Figure 3 (b) shows the DSC curves of CF-GF composites. The release of water during the first heating is more evident for the untreated sample than the post-processed samples. This behavior is in agreement with observed data in TGA (Figure 2 (b)). The two independent Tg's from PA6 and PA of hybrid composites, that would be expected to appear during the first cycle, are not visible (Figure 3 (b)). Only one endothermic step is observed between 50-60 °C. The variation in the melting endothermic peaks sequence with post-processing temperatures for CF-GF composites follows the same tendency as described for GF composites, since crystallization behavior is restricted to the PA6 contribution. Likewise, the crystallization behavior for CF-GF composites during the cooling from the melting is equivalent to GF composites (Figure 3 (a) and (b)), for the same reason. A unique exothermic peak at 160 °C is observed in all the samples. Once the thermal story is removed, the DSC curves during the second heating of GF composites (Figure 3 (a)) are equal for untreated and post-processed samples (Figure 3 (a)). The DSC profiles of hybrid composites during second heating present two endothermic steps, indicated as (b.1) and (b.2) in Figure 3 (b). The first

glass transition is shown between 50°C and 55°C, which is attributed to semi-crystalline polyamide ($T_{g(PA6)}$), while the second between 120°C and 125°C, associated with amorphous polyamide ($T_{g(PA)}$). A closer inspection of the graphs (Figure 3 (b.1) and (b.2)) reveals a systematic increase of both Tg's with the increase of post-processing temperature. Worth to mention that the $T_{g(PA6)}$ of GF composites, where PA6 is the semicrystalline matrix, is observed at 42°C (Figure 2 (a) during second heating), while the $T_{g(PA6)}$ of CF-GF composites appears between 50°C and 55°C (Figure 2 (b)). The increase $T_{g(PA6)}$ in hybrid composites can be associated with the miscibility of two polymers (PA and PA6) in the newly formed interface, but also for the reduction of the plasticizer effect of the water during the post-processing, which is more evident in hybrid composites. From the DSC and TGA analysis is derived the semi-crystalline matrix of GF composite (PA6) seems to be more sensitive to catch water from the environment after post-processing, in comparison to hybrid-matrices composites (PA6 and PA). This could have a negative impact on the mechanical properties (mainly in elastic modulus) of GF composites, due to the plastification effect of the matrix.

Figures 4 (a) and (b) show C-Scan images evolution with increasing the post-processing temperature for GF and CF-GF composite, respectively. White regions indicate large amount of defects in the composite, where the ultrasonic waves are completely attenuated. Dark blue regions (attenuation level less than 6 dB) reveal well consolidation and homogeneity. The intermediates' colors represent different levels of attenuation and hence different levels of consolidation within the material. The highest consolidation for GF composites (Figure 4 (a)) is observed for the sample post-processed at 175°C, while the attenuation is above 20 dB for lower post-processing temperatures. The high content of accumulated air remains in the edges for all post-processing temperatures. However, the consolidation of hybrid composite specimens systematically increases with increasing post-processing temperature. The 3D printed sample treated at 150°C starts to be consolidated in the central region. The attenuation in this region gradually decreases for the coupons treated at 165°C and 175°C, until reaching an attenuation level of 5 dB. The void content with increasing post-processing temperature for GF and CF-GF composites are shown in Figure 4 (c). The porosity values were obtained from X-ray Computed Micro-Tomography (X-CT) data of a piece of 5mm x 5mm x 2mm volume for each sample. Worth to be mentioned that piece was taken from the central region. The untreated sample of GF composite presents 2.5% of porosity, while the void content of CF-GF composites is 4%. These values are lower than reported in the literature for 3D printed CFRC, suggesting amorphous matrix (PA) produces more defects during 3D printing than the semi-crystalline matrix (PA6)[16, 24, 25]. The porosity remains constant for the GF composites treated at 150°C and 165°C, in agreement with the lack of consolidation observed in C-Scan images (Figure 4 (a)). The post-processing at 175°C leads the GF composite to negligible porosity (black line in Figure 4 (c)). The reduction of internal defects occurs at 175°C, when PA6 is close to

Fig. 3 DSC graphs for (a) GF and (b) hybrid CF-GF composites untreated and post-processed at 150°C, 165° and 175°. In each graph are shown first heating, cooling and second heating. The arrows indicate the direction of temperature increase. Enlarged graphs show the evolution of the Tg's with the temperature from (b.1) PA6 and (b.2) PA of hybrid composites.

reaching the melting point (Figure 2 (a)). Figure 4 (c) also shows the porosity evolution of CF-GF composites with post-processing temperatures (red line). The post-processing at 150°C marks the achievement of 0% of porosity for hybrid CF-GF composites is reached, in agreement with the optimized temperature to post-processed 3D printed CFRC[16]. At this temperature, the PA (amorphous matrix) glass transition is overpassed without reaching the melting point of PA6. However, the hybrid composites post-processed at higher temperatures present a porosity of 0%, but they are not able to retain the shape and dimensions of the nominal model.

Figure 5 shows the dimensional variation in length, width and thickness of 3D printed GF and CF-GF composites untreated and post-processed at 150°C,

Fig. 4 C-Scan ultrasonic images for 3D printed (a) GF and (b) CF-GF composites untreated (UT) and post-processed at 150°C, at 165°C and at 175°C. Colour spectrum of the dB losses in the bottom. Dark blue regions indicate low attenuation of ultrasonic waves. (c) Porosity evolution with post-processing temperatures for GF composites (black line) and CF-GF composites (red line).

at 165°C and at 175°C. The control of dimensional accuracy is crucial to ensure the balance between properties and variation in size of the 3D printed samples because it is not practical to obtain large deviations after post-processing. The thickness of 3D printed samples is the most critical variable during the post-processing, since the pressure is applied in the thickness direction. Untreated GF and CF-GF composites present larger thicknesses than the original 3D model, probably due to the difficulty of depositing rigid fibers. The thickness deviation of untreated GF and CF-GF composites are 8% and 15%, respectively (Figure 5 (a) and (b)). This significant difference is because hybrid composites were 3D printed by fixing GF as unique reinforcement, i.e. CF-GF composites were not printed in optimal conditions. The thickness of GF and CF-GF composites decreases systemically with increasing post-processing temperature, which is accompanied by a gradual increase in the width. On the other hand, the sample length remains practically constant upon temperature, may be due to the fact that the specimens were unidirectionally reinforced. The compensation of the deviation observed in z direction after 3D printing is reached at 165°C for GF composite and at 150°C for CF-GF composite. The consistency of the hybrid matrix (CF-GF composites) changes at lower temperatures than the semicrystalline (GF composites), which makes more effective the post-processing at 150°C.

Figure 6 shows the microstructure of CF-GF hybrid composites untreated and post-processed at different temperatures. The images were extracted from the volumes obtained by means of X-CT tomography. Next to the microstructures are plotted the porosity profiles with the separation between the GF layers and the CF layers. The highest concentration of air voids for untreated CF-GF composite is found in the CF layers where the polymer matrix is the amorphous polyamide (PA). This fact confirms that under the same 3D

Fig. 5 The dimensional variation in length, width and thickness of 3D printed (a) GF and (b) CF-GF composites between the nominal design and the post-processing parts at different temperatures

printing conditions, the amorphous matrix produces more defects than semi-crystalline (PA6). Probably, molten PA6 presents lower viscosity than PA and consequently, the material flows easily, reducing the formation of porosity. However, the porosity of CF layers is significantly reduced when the hybrid composites are post-processed at temperatures higher than 150°C. This behavior suggests PA flows better at lower temperatures, and hence the post-processing is more effective at lower temperatures. The remaining defects are located in the inner part of GF layers, as clearly observed on the porosity profiles of samples treated at 150°C and 165°C. As observed in Figures 6, the PA-PA6 interface at these temperatures does not seem a critical region for the accumulation of defects. The porosity of hybrid composites is reduced to quasi-zero at 150°C, while GF-PA6 and CF-PA separately composites under the same post-processing conditions presented 4% and 1.5%, respectively [16]. The hybridization of matrices improves the effectiveness of the post-processing. During 3D printing, the initial contact between deposited beads (intra- and inter-lamina) forms a neck. The miscibility of the bead is limited by the increase of the polymer viscosity during the cooling. In this case, the cooling occurs very fast due to the lack of a heated printing bed. Under post-processing conditions, PA6 maintains its structural integrity and PA overpasses its T_g , which favors the amorphous to accommodate around the semi-crystalline beads, increasing the surface contact and growth neck; and consequently enhancing the diffusion of both polymers. This statement is supported by the systematic increase of T_g of CF-GF composites observed in DSC (Figure 2 (b.1) and (b.2)).

The evolution of the storage modulus and $\tan\delta$ against temperature obtained by DMA for GF and CF-GF composites untreated and post-processed at different temperatures are shown in Figure 7 (a) and (b), respectively. Both GF and CF-GF exhibit a modulus downward step and a broad peak in $\tan\delta$ at -65°C corresponding to β -relaxation probably for both polyamides, PA6 and PA [26]. Figure 7 (a) shows the DMA curves with temperature of GF composites.

Fig. 6 Microstructure of CF-GF hybrid composites untreated and post-processed at 150°C, at 165°C and 175°C. The images were extracted from the volumes obtained by X-CT tomography. Next to the microstructures are shown the porosity profiles with the separation between the GF layers and the CF layers.

The storage modulus increases with increasing post-processing temperature. However, a large drop in the storage modulus accompanied by a concurrent peak in the $\tan\delta$ is observed at 6°C, which does not agree with the T_g determined by DSC (Figure 3). Despite being T_g a range of temperature where the material transits to a rubbery state, 40°C difference in data from DSC to DMA is quite significant. This is probably due to the deconsolidation of the GF composites, observed in C-Scan and the high porosity content (Figure 4 (a) and (c)). During heating, the unbonded GF layers hinder the load transfer within the material, which results in an increase of the loss modulus. This is reflected with the pronounced peak in the $\tan\delta$ (ratio of the loss to the storage), which does not permit to determine the T_g of the material. However, the GF composite post-processed at 175°C presents a notable enhancement of the thermomechanical stability, in agreement with the reduction of porosity under this post-processing condition. Figure 7 (b) shows the storage modulus curves with temperature of CF-GF composites. Two distinct regions are

distinguished: (i) $T_{g(PA6)}$ of semi-crystalline matrix (45°C- 55°C), in agreement with DSC (Figure 3 and (ii) $T_{g(PA)}$ of amorphous matrix (110°C- 125°C), in order of increasing temperature. Both $T_{g(PA6)}$ and $T_{g(PA)}$ systematically increase with post-processing temperature, according to DSC results (Figure 3). The main reason is probably the polymer miscibility in the interface during the post-processing, which translates into a restriction of the chain motion. The improvement of storage modulus and Tg can be hypothetically attributed to a combined effect of different phenomena. First, a significant reduction of internal defects during post-processing, as observed in Figure 4 and Figure 7. Second, an increase of crystallinity in the CF-GF interface; an increase in post-processing temperature produced increases in the melting point, associated with the formation of greater crystals. Third, a drying effect reduces the plastification effect of water in the material, as observed in TGA (Figure 2). This behavior was already reported for 3D printed CF composites [16].

Fig. 7 The evolution of the storage modulus and $\tan \delta$ against temperature for (a) GF and (b) CF-GF composites untreated and post-processed at 150°C, at 165°C and 175°C.

The experimental force-displacement curves under short-beam three point bending load for GF and CF-GF composites, untreated (UT) and post-processed at 150 °C, 165 °C and 175°C are shown in Figures 8 (a) and (b), respectively. Figures 8 (c), (d) and (e) show the tested specimens.

The load curves of the GF composites (Figure 8(a)) do not drop rapidly at any point, and consequently, the interlaminar failure cannot be determined. The lack of consolidation of the GF composites, observed in Figure 4 (a) and 7, may be the reason behind this performance. Probably, the interlaminar failure occurs between layers that are unbonded from each other. Desired interlaminar failure modes are not observed (Figure 8 (c)); only inelastic deformation of tested samples is obtained and a minimal dislocation of the layers is revealed. However, there is a clear effect of post-processing on GF composites,

Fig. 8 Force-displacement curves of the short-beam shear test of 3D printed unidirectional (a) GF and (b) CF-GF composites, untreated and post-processed at 150°C, 165°C and 175°C.

an increase in the bending stiffness with increasing post-processing temperature. Figure 8 (b) shows the load versus displacement curves of the CF-GF composites under three point bending load. In this case, the interlaminar failure is taken with the first force drop in the experimental curves. Consequently, it was possible to determine the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) that was calculated using the following expression:

$$ILSS = 0.75 \cdot \frac{P_m}{b \cdot h} \quad (1)$$

where P_m is the maximum load, b and h are the sample width and thickness. Table 1 shows ILSS values for CF-GF composites untreated and post-processed at 150 °C, 165 °C and 175°C.

Sample	ILSS (MPa)
Untreated	32.4
Post-processed at 150°C	49.8
Post-processed at 165°C	51.3
Post-processed at 175°C	51.6

Table 1 Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) values for CF-GF composites untreated and post-processed at 150 °C, 165 °C and 175°C.

The interlaminar strength for untreated CF-GF composite is 32.4 MPa and increases by approximately 60% for post-processed samples. However, the ILSS remains practically unaffected with increasing post-processing temperature. By inspecting Figure 8 (d), the interlaminar failure in the untreated sample occurs in the CF-GF interface, while the post-processed sample fails at GF-GF interface, where there is more defect accumulation. Under the post-processing conditions, GF layers are not well consolidated which leads to the

Material	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{23}
CF	69.4	5.4	2.7	0.41	0.49
GF	22.	1.45	0.45	0.35	0.45

Table 2 Experimental elastic properties for unidirectional GF and CF post-processed laminates. [11]

first interlaminar failure; consequently, ILSS is approximately kept constant with increasing post-processing temperature.

The short-beam experiments of GF and CF-GF composites have been complemented with numerical simulations based on realistic finite element models. The model of the laminate considers the real dimensions of the coupons, elastic transversely isotropic material properties of each ply, and realistic boundary conditions. These virtual tests implemented in Abaqus [27] follow the methodology explained by Garoz Gómez et al. [11]. The bending stiffness is calculated for the post-processed composites considering the experimental mechanical properties of table 2. Figure 8 (a) shows three slopes that correspond with the simulated bending stiffness of the GF. The slope of the consolidated model is close to the initial part of the experimental curve post-processed at 175 °C. That means that the GF composite has been almost consolidated, however, there is a lack of bond between GF plies as shown in the experiments. This lack of adhesion introduces an inelastic deformation between plies giving a general ductile behavior. The numerical results indicate that the inelastic deformation starts with shear stresses lower than 5 MPa. Two more bending stiffness were represented in figure 8 (a) with degraded transverse and shear modulus 50% or 30% of the consolidated values. It is noteworthy that increasing the post-processed temperature improves these moduli from the untreated one. Analogously, CF-GF composites have been simulated with realistic models. Figure 8 (b) shows three slopes corresponding to models with consolidated and degraded mechanical properties. The bending stiffness of the consolidated model is slightly higher than the experiment post-processed at 175 °C. The different stiffness can be partially explained due to the lack of adhesion between GF plies. The post-processed experiments show a ductile behavior because of the inelastic deformation between GF plies until its break. The bending stiffness improves with the post-processing because transverse and shear modulus increase from the initial values of the untreated composite.

4 Conclusion

The hybrid CF-GF composites fabricated by FFF technique presented two main drawbacks: the significant void content and the poor adhesion between layers of different matrices. A thermal/low-pressure post-processing step improved both weaknesses. The post-processing success depends on hybridizing the polymer matrices used for the GF and CF filaments. GFs are embedded in PA6, semicrystalline polyamide, and CF in amorphous polyamide (PA). The similar nature of polymers allowed the interpenetration of polymer chains in

the interface during the post-processing of CF-GF hybrid composites at temperatures between the glass transition of PA and the melting temperature of PA6. Keeping the temperature below PA6 melting temperature was essential to maintain the dimensional stability of the 3D parts, but higher than PA glass transition, which reduced the voids, at a lower temperature than GF 3D parts and favored the chain diffusion, improving the adhesion of GF and CF layers. This better adhesion, summed to void reduction and the minor plasticizer effect due to the lower water content, produced much better consolidated CF-GF 3D printed composites. Indeed, the hybridization of two different polymers during thermal post-processing has been revealed as an excellent strategy to improve the consolidation of hybrid 3D printed composites, whether polymer matrices are miscible. Future works are planning to explore this idea in other polymer couples and to extent this post-processing to complex structure.

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